

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF AXIOLOGICAL APPROACH IN ORGANIZING EDUCATION LESSONS

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Abstract. *This article reflects on the importance of education today, the problem of studying the inner potential of a person aimed at increasing the dignity of a person in recent years in society. The problems and issues of education are more important than the system of ideas in all periods of human history, and the struggles for the mind and faith of a person are manifested in the form of influencing young people through educational methods. It has been said that the education system has become the main goal in the process of instilling feelings of love for people in the psyche of our youth. In addition, the development of axiology as a teaching in pedagogy, as well as the role and importance of the axiological approach in the organization of education classes, are also widely covered.*

Keywords: *education, mind, thought, activity, work, approach, value.*

INTRODUCTION

Humanity can never live without being separated from the outside world, changes, developments, happenings, events, processes in the surrounding world or without feeling them. And it is closely related to them. States, peoples, nations, socio-political forces, relations between them, especially ideological influences in social processes, cannot fail to affect people's consciousness, thinking and worldview, and will definitely show their influence. On the other hand, the ideas and ideologies that occupy the mind and heart of people cannot be formed, they cannot become a powerful inner force that serves the development of the society, the future of the nation and the people without education and training. In this world, in recent years, the problem of learning the inner potential of a person, aimed at increasing the value of a person, has become one of the priority areas of pedagogy, and the main concepts of educational mechanisms: personal health, organizing one's own activities, self-development. Concepts such as self-determination in the community and self-realization in the infrastructures of society indicate that the individual is in the position of universal values. This is the priority principle, it is the humanity inherent in the nature of our society, the mentality of our nation, and it is the fundamental basis of the formation of our national idea. Turning the educational system into the main goal is the urgent task of today.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

The "Strategy of Development" implemented in our country is a new stage of reforms, in which the spiritual, social and economic support of the population and youth occupies a leading place. In this place, based on economic and socio-political value and education, material and moral support work was started.

I. Kant played a major role in the development of axiology as a teaching in pedagogy, he placed Man in the center of his philosophy, which, in fact, opened a new stage in the development of axiological knowledge. Kant ends the era of considering tradition and value as products, and with Kant begins the stage of understanding value for man.

In the field of education, many scientists have done some high-level work. Books written by S.P. Azarov "Teaching Method" and "Learner-Centered Teaching: Five Key Changes to Practice" by Maryellen Weimer are of theoretical and scientific importance.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The article provides information about the importance of axiological approaches in education classes, including the role of education in the education system, the need for it, and the importance of improving the quality of education among the current issues of social importance.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

It is known that, according to its essence, education is expressed in broad and narrow terms and is applied in social life. In a broad sense, education is a special process that transfers socio-cultural experiences from generation to generation with a specific goal in mind and creates conditions for the development of a person.

In our country, young people are our future, they are the successors of the work of our parents and ancestors. Our main goal is to educate a perfect person based on national and spiritual values. When we say a perfect person, we mean first of all people who have a broad worldview, are patriotic, can think independently, are an example to others with their behavior, are responsible and healthy. As understanding takes place in the process of axiology, the problems of developing axiological value system in young people in social infrastructures, educating them as specialists with high morals, humane qualities, and deep knowledge of their profession are leading issues of scientific-pedagogical research as education and values are fundamentally different. Natural, material, spiritual, socio-political, moral values stand out among them.

Values are an important factor in the purification and development of our society. The "Strategy of Development" implemented in our country is a new stage of reforms, in which the moral, social and economic support of the population and youth takes the leading place. In this place, on the basis of economic and socio-political values, the employees of state agencies went from house to house to listen to peoples' pain, ease their burden, and support them materially and morally. The ideological basis of our national heritage is the study of the factors that contribute to the education of the individual and his spiritual needs.

If the creativity of our ancestors was aimed at personal interests, at the same time, all the innovations implemented in our independent country are intended to serve the future of mankind. The ideological harmony of the modern educational system and the national heritage means the need to rely on the spiritual and educational grounds of the national heritage during the educational process.

In this regard, it is possible to say something about the society and its education in the pamphlet "Maslag of the residents of Fazil city": "Each man is so constituted by nature that he needs many things in order to live and to reach the highest level of maturity, which he cannot acquire alone, but to acquire them he needs a community of people". This, in turn, shows that education is also aimed at collective unity. From this point of view, the importance of the spiritual heritage of the scholars and thinkers of the past in the education of the young generation is incomparable even today. Problems and issues of education have a great place in the system of ideas of all periods of human history. Struggles for people's consciousness and faith are also manifested in the form of influencing young people through educational methods. For this reason, raising a physically healthy, spiritually mature person remains one of the main principles of the national independence ideology of Uzbekistan. It is known that the main purpose of the national

model is to educate a perfect person. This is one of the main concepts and tasks. In this regard, the importance of training classes is incomparable. When it comes to education classes, it is worth noting the following: education classes are one of the classes that are held in order to provide students with spiritual, physical, intellectual and social development. Education helps to teach students knowledge, to form human values, to strengthen ideological thinking and to increase experience in social issues. Through these lessons, students learn to respond to problems and tasks necessary for their development and self-development by learning scientific and practical knowledge. Educational lessons are very important for students, because through these lessons they develop the ability to master themselves, express their thoughts, ask for and learn advice, communicate with society, and gain experience in a community. Education teaches students to be fair, kind, respectful, cooperative, ask for advice, and learn from their mistakes. Education also focuses on physical development of students. It provides an opportunity for students to improve their physical development, pay attention to health and spend productive personal time through sports, recreation and other physical activities. It is also recommended for the spiritual development of students. At the same time, by studying language, literature, art, music, spirituality and culture of enlightenment, students can get acquainted with their spiritual values and interests, form values and strengthen their human ideal understanding. The educational lesson also strives for the social development of students. In order for them to become people who are reliable in the community, respect others, are ready to cooperate, have improved their creative and speaking skills, and are able to analyze social issues, education classes have a great place. The curriculum also focuses on the personal development of students. They provide a guide for self-understanding and self-development, determination of their abilities and requirements, self-confidence, mastery of immediate tasks. For all these reasons, parenting is important for students' overall development and mastery in their personal processes. These classes help to develop students in academic, physical, spiritual, social and personal directions and guide them to form themselves as complete individuals. It can also be done through engaging and animated methods that give special and personal attention to students' self-awareness and knowledge development. These methods help students demonstrate their learning process and achieve their goals. An education class also allows students to learn life skills such as personal finance, business, health, responsible parenting, community service, and more. Through these classes, students can gain the necessary knowledge and skills to understand their responsibilities, learn life skills, solve work-related problems, and choose a career of their choice. The main goal of our national model is to educate a perfect person. Scientists of our republic are putting forward their own concepts in this matter as well. In particular, a spiritually perfect person acts on the basis of intelligence. Among them, youth education is considered a very important factor for the development of our country. Education is a broad concept, and there are many types and approaches to its research, including the axiological approach. The axiological approach occupies a deep place in education and in the organization of education classes.

The role of the axiological approach in the organization of educational lessons is very important. Axiology deals with the study of moral values, spirituality, dignity, good and evil, achieving goals and objectives, self-legitimacy, and other spiritual essences. The axiological approach helps to determine the value and costs of the activities organized in the educational process. This approach takes place in the formation of students' moral, ethical, aesthetic, human, national and other values. Axiology includes a body of scientific research and principles related to

teaching values, spirituality, and the skills of freedom, valuing humanity, and teaching a purposeful life. When it comes to the role of axiological approach in educational classes, it can be said that it helps to form feelings of cooperation, respect and peace among students. This approach helps students develop valuable behaviors and habits. Its main goal is to teach students to value humanity and treat them with respect. The importance of the axiological approach in educational lessons is that it teaches to give dignity to humanity and to look at life with a purpose, to make students against injustice, oppression and discord, to give dignity to humanity, and to have the necessary values and spirituality to solve social problems. An axiological approach teaches students how to study their own lives, value humanity, discuss social issues, develop valuable behavior and cooperation, and contribute to value humanity. The axiological approach in educational lessons allows students to understand moral values and freedoms, to develop valuable behavior, to solve social problems, and to teach analysis and conclusions. This will help students' personal development, fight against injustice and oppression, solve social problems and preserve the dignity of humanity. The axiological approach includes the basic principles of organizing educational lessons. These principles are based on teaching students values of behavior, justice, freedom, cooperation, peace and respect for others. These characteristics are learned by students and affect their personal and social development. The first task of the axiological approach is to acquaint students with spiritual values and increase their overall human values. By studying values, students learn how to value themselves, others, and the world. This gives students an opportunity to strengthen and develop their intelligence and understanding. Students should learn these values and understand the importance of being fair and opposing oppression in solving social problems. Such knowledge and understanding will help them solve social problems and learn to cooperate with others. This approach also underpins teaching students to value humanity and look at life with purpose. This helps students develop valuable behaviors and learn important parts of achieving their goals. At the same time, it leads students to solve human problems, discuss important social issues, and develop important and good qualities for humanity. This approach not only affects the personal and social development of students, but also ensures that they can appreciate themselves and the environment, society and other factors. At the same time, the role and importance of the axiological approach in the organization of education classes are very great. Through an axiological approach, students are able to appreciate themselves, others and the world, and are empowered to develop themselves. The axiological approach in educational lessons helps students to focus on universal values, humanity, beliefs, literature, culture, nation and other important values. Also, the axiological approach helps students develop self-confidence and self-esteem. This view helps students to form essences related to humanity, literature, ethics, cooperation, work, faith, law and other spiritual values. This is used in the personal and community development of students. At the same time, it is also important to teach students the importance of self-esteem and the development of good qualities of self in education classes. This approach not only instills in students a sense of respect and kindness to other people, but also teaches them to obey laws, to pay attention to literature, culture and nationality. In addition, the importance of the axiological approach in education classes is seen in helping students to direct their goals, to identify their desires and wishes. This approach provides an opportunity to understand and develop students' values and goals.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that the axiological approach to the organization of education classes, first of all, creates the need to improve the mechanisms of education, and this is a social need and pedagogical problem, based on the strengthening of its national and universal ground, to provide students and young people with knowledge and skills based on the requirements of the time and world standards. along with providing information, inculcates in them a high spiritual culture, morals and enlightenment, knowledge, manners, qualities and understanding. The axiological approach in educational lessons helps students to focus on universal values, humanity, beliefs, literature, culture, nation and other important values. This approach is important in forming and developing students' goals, desires, and wishes.

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